

When Robots Are Abandoned: Post-discontinuation Sustainability as an Epistemological Problem

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Abstract

Sustainability in social robotics is often addressed at the level of individual artifacts, design choices, or efficiency metrics. However, social robots are embedded over time in socio-technical systems composed of users, infrastructures, routines, and shared practices, within which their (re-)use, maintenance, and disposal are collectively shaped. Under these conditions, sustainability can be adequately explored not only at the level of robotic artifacts, but also at the level of the socio-technical systems in which robots are embedded.

Starting from this premise, the paper investigates technological discontinuation in social robotics as a critical site for analyzing sustainability. It explores the conditions under which post-discontinuation configurations can generate system-level regulation leading to sustainability-relevant outcomes after support withdrawal.

The analysis builds on prior work on AIBO, where post-discontinuation sustainability was interpreted through a self-organizational framework describing system-level regulation involving users, repair practices, and material infrastructures. While this case showed the heuristic power of a systemic approach, it left unanswered whether self-organization can function as a general descriptive framework for system sustainability in social robotics.

To address this issue, the paper subjects the self-organizational framework to a stress test through a controlled comparison of the post-discontinuation cases of AIBO and Moxie, characterized by sharply different organizational dependencies. The comparison suggests that self-organization operates not as a general framework, but as a *diagnostic analytical device*, identifying the organizational conditions under which system-level regulation can stabilize, or remain inhibited. On this basis, the paper examines when post-discontinuation sustainability can, and cannot, emerge in hybrid human–robot ecologies.

Keywords: Sustainability; Social Robotics; Self-organization; Socio-technical Systems; Hybrid Human–Robot Ecologies; Post-discontinuation Dynamics

1 Introduction

The growing integration of social robots into everyday human practices raises a set of questions that are not reducible to technological performance or user acceptance alone. When robotic systems are designed to interact, accompany, and support human activities over extended periods of time, they become embedded in networks of social relations, routines, expectations, and forms of care. In this sense, social robots participate in hybrid human–robot ecologies (e.g.,

[1]), where artificial agents are entangled with human actors, material infrastructures, and social practices, giving rise to genuinely socio-technical configurations (e.g., [2, 3]). Within such hybrid ecologies, the question of sustainability cannot be addressed solely at the level of individual artifacts or design-stage optimization; it also requires a perspective capable of investigating system-level dynamics.

In line with this premise, processes associated with technological discontinuation provide a complementary entry point for investigating sustainability in social robotics.

Social robots are typically developed within industrial and commercial ecosystems characterized by rapid innovation cycles, platform dependency, and planned obsolescence. As a result, technological discontinuation — such as the withdrawal of production, maintenance, or infrastructural support — represents a structurally recurrent condition in social robotics, highly relevant for inquiries into robot sustainability. Discontinuation confronts users and communities not only with the functional limits of robotic systems, but also with their environmental implications, particularly in terms of waste generation and premature disposal.

At the same time, discontinuation does not affect all hybrid human–robot ecologies in the same way. In some configurations, the withdrawal of industrial support triggers coordinated collective practices aimed at maintaining, repairing, repurposing, or otherwise extending the usable life of robotic artifacts. These practices — ranging from informal repair networks to forms of shared stewardship — can be interpreted as sustainability-relevant outcomes, insofar as they contribute to lifecycle extension and mitigate environmentally costly replacement dynamics. Importantly, such outcomes are not properties of the robot taken in isolation, but effects of the organizational dynamics of the surrounding socio-technical system.

From this systemic standpoint, post-discontinuation dynamics are not marginal phenomena, but epistemologically privileged sites for analyzing sustainability in social robotics. It is under conditions of disruption that the organizational interdependencies of hybrid human–robot ecologies become visible and analyzeable. Moments of discontinuity expose whether, and under which conditions, coordinated collective dynamics arise that regulate the socio-technical system, or whether such dynamics are structurally inhibited. In some configurations, these system-level regulatory dynamics can generate sustainability-relevant outcomes — most notably practices that extend the usable life of robotic artifacts — while in others such outcomes remain unattainable. In this sense, post-discontinuation situations allow sustainability-relevant processes to be investigated as emergent and contingent outcomes of socio-technical organization. This line of inquiry complements existing artifact-centered approaches by considering sustainability as a potential emergent system-level behavior, which may arise when a socio-technical ecology responds to perturbations — in this case, technological discontinuation — through distributed forms of regulation.

To account for these dynamics, previous work has adopted self-organization as a framework for interpreting sustainability in hybrid human–robot ecologies [3, 4]. Drawing on a systemic and cybernetic tradition, the self-organizational approach focuses on how coherence, coordination, and regulation can emerge from distributed interactions among heterogeneous components, without centralized control (e.g., [5, 6, 7]). Applied to social robotics, self-

organization shifts the analytical focus from individual artifacts to the organizational patterns that sustain — or fail to sustain — socio-technical systems over time. In our earlier research, this framework was applied to the post-discontinuation trajectory of Sony’s AIBO robotic dog, a social companion robot designed for long-term interaction and deeply embedded in everyday use contexts. Following the gradual withdrawal of production, maintenance, and official repair services, the AIBO case made visible how forms of coordinated collective engagement — such as community-based repair initiatives, component reuse, and shared stewardship — supported the continued operation of the robots beyond corporate support. Crucially, this analysis highlighted that sustainability-relevant outcomes emerged at the level of socio-technical organization, rather than as intrinsic properties of the robotic artifact, and informed a set of design-oriented guidelines for fostering post-discontinuation sustainability in social robotics [4].

However, this single-case analysis, while showing the heuristic value of a self-organizational perspective, did not establish its explanatory adequacy beyond that specific configuration. In particular, it left open an important methodological question: *how robust is this framework across different configurations of social robotics discontinuation?* More specifically, *to what extent do sustainability-relevant outcomes depend on the organizational conditions of a given hybrid ecology, rather than on individual, contextual, or contingent factors external to its socio-technical organization?*

This paper addresses these questions by subjecting the self-organization framework to an explicit “epistemological stress test”, proposed here as a controlled comparative operation aimed at probing the scope and limits of the self-organizational approach across socio-technical configurations characterized by different organizational dependencies. Specifically, the stress test implemented in this paper extends our analysis of the AIBO case through a controlled comparison with a second case, Embodied’s Moxie, selected because its organizational dependencies differ structurally from those observed in AIBO. By contrasting these two configurations, the analysis tests whether and how self-organization can account for post-discontinuation trajectories under markedly different conditions, particularly with respect to the emergence or inhibition of collective regulatory dynamics and lifecycle extension, construed here not as a comprehensive sustainability metric, but as a minimal and observable system-level indicator of stabilized collective regulation.

The aim of the comparison is not to generalize across social robotics, nor to assess the relative success of specific products. Instead, the two cases are treated as epistemological probes through which the conditions under which self-organizational dynamics can be meaningfully identified — or structurally inhibited — are analytically clarified. By contrasting configurations that enable or constrain collective regulatory dynamics, the analysis seeks to specify when and how hybrid human–robot ecologies can generate environmentally relevant outcomes in situations of technological discontinuation.

The contribution of this paper is threefold. First, it reframes sustainability in social robotics by treating post-discontinuation situations as analytically privileged sites for investigating sustainability-relevant dynamics in hybrid human–robot ecologies. Second, it subjects self-

organization to an explicit epistemological stress test, using a controlled comparison between two discontinuation cases characterized by markedly different organizational dependencies, thereby clarifying the scope and limits of the framework. Third, by focusing on lifecycle extension as a sustainability-relevant outcome, the paper identifies the organizational conditions under which post-discontinuation collective regulation can stabilize — or remain structurally inhibited — without proposing prescriptive design solutions. Based on these outcomes, this study contributes to ongoing debates in social robotics concerning long-term interaction, responsibility, and sustainability beyond deployment and use phases.

The paper is organized as follows. *Section 2* introduces the methodological framework of the epistemological stress test and outlines the comparative research design. *Section 3* analyzes the AIBO case as a reference configuration for post-discontinuation sustainability. *Section 4* examines the Moxie case as a contrasting epistemological configuration that places the self-organizational framework under stress. *Section 5* discusses the comparative findings and their implications for the epistemic status of self-organization in social robotics. *Section 6* articulates the conditions shaping the stabilization of post-discontinuation sustainability in hybrid human–robot ecologies. *Section 7* concludes by summarizing the main insights and outlining directions for future research.

2 Methodology: Epistemological Stress Test

2.1 Epistemological case studies: scope and limits

This paper adopts epistemological case analysis as its methodological strategy. Within complex systems research, this approach is commonly used to examine whether general self-organizational frameworks can adequately account for the dynamics observed in particular systems. Rather than treating cases as empirical samples or illustrative examples, epistemological case analysis mobilizes particular cases as analytical probes through which the explanatory scope and limits of a theoretical framework can be evaluated. Accordingly, this study does not aim to produce new empirical data, but to re-analyze existing post-discontinuation trajectories as epistemological cases, in order to test the scope and limits of a self-organizational framework applied to social robotics.

This methodological strategy belongs to a well-established lineage in cybernetic epistemology and, more in general, complex systems research, where concrete biological, social, and ecological systems have been systematically analyzed to test self-organizational principles across heterogeneous domains. Seminal contributions — most notably those by authors such as Ilya Prigogine [8], Francisco Varela [9], Eric Jantsch [10], Stuart Kauffman [6], Fritjof Capra [11] and Pier Luigi Luisi [12, 13] — have employed case-based analyses not to derive empirical generalizations, but to assess whether system-level patterns of organization, regulation, and coherence can be identified beyond domain-specific mechanisms. Across these works, cases function as epistemic probes for identifying organizational regularities — i.e., recurrent patterns of system-level coherence and regulation — beyond domain-specific mechanisms.

Within this lineage, Varela's work provides a particularly rigorous formulation of epistemological case analysis. In *Principles of Biological Autonomy* [9], as well as in subsequent writings, organizational autonomy and its defining features are articulated as cross-domain organizational patterns whose identification depends on explicit epistemic criteria. In particular, organizational closure is introduced as a criterion for evaluating whether different systems, at different levels of reality, instantiate forms of autonomous organization.

The present study applies the epistemological case approach, in its Varelian configuration, to specific instances of social robot discontinuation. These cases are treated as epistemological cases through which to test whether the self-organizational framework (see *Section 2.3*) can be meaningfully used to describe the dynamics through which hybrid human–robot ecologies respond to discontinuity-induced perturbations. In particular, the analysis focuses on whether distributed interactions among human actors, social robots, related infrastructures, and practices give rise to system-level regulatory dynamics, and on how such dynamics contribute to — or inhibit — forms of sustainability-relevant organization following situations of social robot discontinuation.

2.2 Epistemological stress test: rationale

The adoption of epistemological case analysis raises a further methodological question concerning the scope and robustness of the self-organizational framework employed in this study. While the analysis of a single epistemological case can make visible the internal coherence and heuristic value of a theoretical model, it cannot, on its own, clarify the conditions under which that model remains applicable, nor the limits beyond which its descriptive power breaks down. For this reason, epistemological case analysis is often complemented by comparative strategies explicitly designed to stress-test a framework across heterogeneous configurations (e.g., [14]).

In this study, the notion of epistemological stress test is used to define a methodological operation aimed at probing the resilience and limits of a self-organizational model when applied beyond the specific conditions in which it has previously shown descriptive adequacy. This stress test does not take the form of empirical validation or statistical generalization. Rather, it consists in exposing the framework to cases characterized by markedly different organizational interdependencies, in order to assess whether the same conceptual descriptors can still account for observed system-level dynamics, or whether their applicability proves contingent on specific structural conditions.

The need for such a stress test emerges directly from the analysis of the AIBO case [4]. In that context, self-organization provided a coherent account of how coordinated collective practices emerged following technological discontinuation, enabling forms of robot lifecycle extension and sustainability-relevant organization. However, this outcome may depend on a particular constellation of organizational features, including the distribution of technical knowledge, access to repair infrastructures, the permeability of technological boundaries, and the capacity of user communities to coordinate practices of maintenance and reuse. Without a comparative assessment, it remains unclear whether these dynamics reflect general self-organizational

properties of hybrid human–robot ecologies, or whether they are tightly bound to the specific organizational configuration in which AIBO was embedded.

The epistemological stress test introduced here is therefore designed to disentangle framework-level explanatory power from case-specific enabling conditions. By comparing post-discontinuation trajectories across cases with structurally different organizational dependencies, the analysis seeks to determine whether self-organization can function as a general descriptive framework for sustainability-relevant dynamics, or whether its applicability is constrained to a limited subset of socio-technical configurations.

Importantly, this stress test is not intended to establish success or failure, nor to rank cases in normative terms. Its purpose is analytical and epistemological: to clarify under which organizational conditions self-organizational descriptors — such as regulation, coordination, and system-level coherence — can be meaningfully identified, and under which conditions they fail to emerge. In this sense, the stress test functions as a methodological device for refining the scope, limits, and epistemic status of self-organization as a framework for analyzing hybrid human–robot ecologies in situations of technological discontinuation.

This rationale provides the basis for the comparative research design introduced in the following section, where two cases of social robot discontinuation are selected and positioned so as to systematically probe the descriptive reach of the self-organizational model.

2.3 The self-organizational framework under stress: epistemological descriptors

Although self-organization has been introduced in robotics as a design strategy for adaptive behavior (e.g., [15]), the present study adopts a system-level perspective, focusing on post-discontinuation socio-technical ecologies rather than on intra-robot adaptive mechanisms. The epistemological stress test developed in this work relies on a generic model of autonomous or self-organizing systems articulated in Damiano [14, 16; see also 17, 18]. This model was constructed by identifying conceptual convergences among pioneering scientific approaches to self-organization [19], and was explicitly designed to be applicable across heterogeneous domains. In this context, “generic” indicates that the model is independent of specific levels or domains of application; it provides organizational descriptors for analyzing heterogeneous systems by focusing on the relational organization that constitutes them, rather than on their material substrate or on domain-specific mechanisms. According to Damiano [14, 16], this generic model aligns with the autonomous system model proposed by Francisco Varela in *Principles of Biological Autonomy* [9], which addressed the challenge of describing heterogeneous autonomous systems — biological, social, technical, or ecological — in a unified manner by identifying their organizational features independently of their specific domain (Varela, [9], p. 55).

In this lineage, autonomy defines self-organizing systems; it is the emergent organizational property through which a system constitutes itself as a coherent, dynamic, and integrated unit, characterized by processes of self-constitution and self-maintenance, and grounded in the relational interdependencies among its components, without reliance on centralized control. The defining feature of the self-organizational framework is therefore the focus on organization,

rather than on material substrate or functional performance. This makes it particularly suitable for the analysis of hybrid human–robot ecologies, where human actors, artificial agents, technical infrastructures, and social practices are intertwined in non-trivial ways, and where system-level dynamics cannot be reduced to the properties or intentions of individual components.

In order to operationalize the framework for comparative analysis, this study adopts a restricted set of organizational descriptors derived from the generic model of autonomous or self-organizing systems. Within this methodological setting, these descriptors operate as *epistemological devices*: they function as analytical criteria through which post-discontinuation dynamics can be assessed, rather than as explanatory mechanisms tied to a specific domain. Accordingly, the descriptors are introduced not as theoretical positions to be defended, but as analytical operators for the comparative assessment of post-discontinuation dynamics. Their role is to enable a systematic evaluation of whether, and under which organizational conditions, self-organizational regulatory dynamics can be meaningfully identified in socio-technical configurations affected by technological discontinuity.

Organization. Within the self-organizational framework, organization refers to the relational structuring of heterogeneous components into a coherent system. Organization is not reducible to the presence of individual elements — such as robots, users, or infrastructures — but concerns the patterned interdependencies that bind these elements together. In the present study, organization functions as a criterion for identifying whether post-discontinuation interactions give rise to a reconfigured but coherent socio-technical ecology, rather than remaining a collection of isolated responses.

Emergence. This notion designates the appearance of system-level properties or dynamics that cannot be reduced to the properties or actions of individual components. In the context of social robot discontinuation, emergence is used to assess whether collective practices — such as repair networks, software initiatives, or forms of shared stewardship — generate new modes of coordination that exceed individual responses to disruption. Emergence thus marks the transition from local reactions to system-level regulatory patterns.

Autonomy. This concept defines an organizational property of systems capable of defining their own dynamics and regulating it in the face of perturbations. Importantly, autonomy does not imply independence from the environment, but rather the capacity to maintain coherence through internally generated regulatory processes. In this study, autonomy functions as a criterion for evaluating whether post-discontinuation socio-technical configurations can sustain themselves without relying on continued corporate support, or whether they remain structurally dependent on external control.

Co-evolution. This notion refers to the reciprocal coupling between a system and its environment, through which both are mutually shaped over time. Applied to hybrid human–robot ecologies, co-evolution captures how user practices, technical infrastructures, cultural meanings, and regulatory constraints interact dynamically following discontinuation. This descriptor is used to assess whether post-discontinuation dynamics involve adaptive

reconfigurations that reshape both the socio-technical system and its surrounding context, or whether adaptation is constrained to narrow functional adjustments.

Organizational closure. Closure occupies a central epistemic role within the Varelian self-organizational framework. It designates the circular network of interdependencies through which a system produces and sustains itself as a recognizable organizational unit. Closure does not imply physical isolation or self-sufficiency; rather, it functions as a criterion for identifying whether the processes that constitute a system are recursively linked in a way that stabilizes its identity (e.g., [9, 16, 20]). In the present analysis, closure is used to evaluate whether post-discontinuation configurations give rise to closed loops of interaction — such as those linking affective attachment, technical practices, and infrastructural support — or whether such loops remain incomplete or fragile.

Together, these descriptors provide a coherent set of epistemic criteria for analyzing post-discontinuation dynamics in hybrid human–robot ecologies. Rather than presupposing sustainability-relevant outcomes, they enable an assessment of whether collective regulatory processes emerge, under which organizational conditions they do so, and to what extent they contribute to outcomes such as robot lifecycle extension. The following sections apply these descriptors to two cases of social robot discontinuation — AIBO and Moxie — in order to subject the self-organizational framework adopted to an explicit comparative stress test.

2.4 Comparative research design: modeling post-discontinuation dynamics in AIBO and Moxie

The epistemological stress test defined in the previous parts of *Section 2* is implemented through a comparative research design based on two cases of social robot discontinuation. The comparison is not intended to establish empirical generalizations, nor to evaluate the relative merits or failures of specific robotic products. Rather, it is designed to probe the explanatory reach of the self-organizational framework under conditions characterized by structurally different organizational dependencies.

The two cases — respectively related to Sony’s AIBO robotic dog and Embodied’s Moxie companion robot — are selected because they share a set of relevant baseline features while differing markedly in the organizational conditions that shape their post-discontinuation trajectories. In both cases, the robots were designed for long-term interaction and social engagement, became embedded in everyday practices, and elicited sustained forms of attachment and care. Moreover, both cases are characterized by a moment of technological discontinuation that constitutes a comparable perturbation at the level of the surrounding socio-technical ecology.

At the same time, the organizational configurations in which AIBO and Moxie were embedded differ in ways that are directly relevant to the self-organizational framework under test. These differences concern, among other aspects, the accessibility of technical knowledge and repair practices, the degree of openness or closure of software and hardware infrastructures, the distribution of control between manufacturers and user communities, and the conditions under which collective coordination among users can plausibly emerge following discontinuation (see

Section 3, Section 4 and Section 5). As a result, the two cases instantiate distinct boundary conditions for the emergence of system-level regulatory dynamics.

Within this design, technological discontinuation functions as a common source of perturbation, while organizational dependency constitutes the primary dimension along which the cases are contrasted. The comparison is thus structured to examine whether, and under which conditions, the analytical descriptors derived from the self-organizational framework — organization, emergence, autonomy, co-evolution, and closure — and the system-level regulatory dynamics they make visible (e.g., coordination and system-level regulation) can be meaningfully identified across configurations with different organizational constraints.

Methodologically, the two cases are treated as epistemological cases rather than as empirical samples. The analysis draws on heterogeneous publicly available sources, including historical reconstructions, ethnographic accounts, technical documentation, and user-generated materials. These sources are not employed to produce exhaustive descriptions, but to assess whether the self-organizational framework provides a coherent and discriminating account of post-discontinuation dynamics in each configuration.

By placing a case in which self-organization has already demonstrated explanatory adequacy alongside a case characterized by more restrictive organizational dependencies, the comparative design enables a systematic assessment of the scope and limits of the framework. In this way, the comparison serves as the core methodological device through which the epistemological stress test is conducted, preparing the ground for the formulation of targeted research questions in the following section.

2.5 Research questions

Building on the epistemological case approach (*Section 2.1*), the logic of the epistemological stress test (*Section 2.2*), the self-organizational framework under stress (*Section 2.3*), and the comparative research design (*Section 2.4*), this study is guided by the following research questions.

RQ1. *To what extent can the generic model of autonomous or self-organizing systems coherently account for post-discontinuation dynamics in hybrid human–robot ecologies characterized by different organizational dependencies?*

This question targets the explanatory adequacy of the self-organizational framework when applied beyond the conditions in which it has previously shown heuristic value. In particular, it asks whether the same analytical descriptors — organization, emergence, autonomy, co-evolution, and closure — can be meaningfully identified across discontinuation cases with structurally different socio-technical configurations.

RQ2. *Which organizational conditions enable, or inhibit, the emergence of collective regulatory dynamics following social robot discontinuation?*

This question focuses on the conditions of possibility for self-organizational processes to arise in post-discontinuation contexts. Rather than presupposing sustainability-relevant outcomes, it examines how differences in organizational interdependencies — such as infrastructural

openness, access to repair practices, and the distribution of coordination capacities — shape the emergence or suppression of collective regulation.

RQ3. *Under which conditions do post-discontinuation regulatory dynamics give rise to sustainability-relevant outcomes, specifically in terms of lifecycle extension?*

This question links the epistemological stress test to the paper’s sustainability focus. It investigates whether, and under which organizational configurations, collective regulatory dynamics translate into practices that extend the usable life of robotic artifacts, thereby mitigating environmentally costly replacement trajectories.

In combination, these research questions do not aim to generalize across social robotics, nor to evaluate the success of specific products. Instead, they function as epistemological probes, designed to clarify the scope and limits of self-organization as an analytical framework for interpreting sustainability-relevant dynamics in hybrid human–robot ecologies under conditions of technological discontinuation.

3 Case I: AIBO¹

3.1 AIBO hybrid community as a socio-technical ecology

Sony’s AIBO is a robotic dog designed as a companion for long-term social interaction with human users, developed and manufactured between 1999 and 2006, with over 150,000 units sold worldwide. The name “AIBO” echoes the Japanese *aibō* (“friend” or “companion”), reflecting its intended role as a robotic pet rather than as a utilitarian device. Through a combination of sensors, embodied behaviours, and adaptive software (AIBOLife), AIBO supports verbal and physical interaction and can develop a distinctive interactional profile over time, shaped by repeated engagement with its owner.

Beyond its technical features, AIBO has been widely documented as a long-term companion embedded in everyday practices of care, routine, and affective engagement, rather than as a short-lived consumer artifact (e.g., [21, 22, 23]). Users commonly attributed to AIBO forms of continuity, individuality, and relational presence, treating it as an entity requiring attention, maintenance, and emotional investment over time (e.g., [24]). This sustained affective engagement played a crucial role in stabilizing interactional routines and motivating practices of care that extended well beyond initial purchase or novelty effects.

Analytically, these features situate AIBO within a hybrid human–robot socio-technical ecology, in which continued interaction does not depend solely on the robotic artifact itself, but on a

¹ A more detailed and systematic discussion of the AIBO case can be found in [3, 4], where sustainability in social robotics is articulated through an epistemological reflection on the “robosphere”, understood as the emerging socio-technical ecology formed by long-lived, socially embedded robotic systems and their organizational interdependencies with users, human practices, technical infrastructures, and shared forms of care and maintenance. In the present paper, the AIBO case is mobilized in a more circumscribed way, focusing on post-discontinuation dynamics to test the scope and limits of a self-organizational framework for sustainability in social robotics.

distributed set of organizational conditions. These include the availability of repair infrastructures, access to technical knowledge, shared practices of maintenance and reuse, and socially mediated meanings attached to the robot as a companion. From this perspective, AIBO is not simply an object of interaction, but a relational node within a broader configuration that intertwines affective attachment, technical support, and collective practices. It is precisely this organizational embedding that makes AIBO a paradigmatic case for analyzing post-discontinuation dynamics through a self-organizational framework.

3.2 Technological discontinuation as systemic perturbation

In January 2006, Sony announced the discontinuation of AIBO's production. Over the following years, corporate support was progressively reduced, culminating in the complete termination of official maintenance and repair services in 2014. While this withdrawal directly affected the technical functioning of individual AIBO units, its broader impact was organizational rather than merely functional.

The discontinuation disrupted the infrastructural and organizational conditions that had sustained the AIBO socio-technical ecology over time. By withdrawing centralized repair services, spare-part supply, and institutional support, Sony's exit exposed the extent to which long-term interaction with AIBO depended on a network of interdependencies extending beyond the artifact itself. What was perturbed was not simply a product lifecycle, but a configuration of practices, expectations, and material supports that had enabled the continued existence of AIBO as a companion within everyday life.

From an epistemological standpoint, this moment of discontinuation constitutes a privileged perturbation, as it renders visible the organizational dependencies underlying the persistence of the hybrid ecology. The question raised by this disruption is not whether individual users could continue to operate their robots in isolation, but whether collective regulatory dynamics could emerge at the level of the socio-technical system to compensate for the loss of centralized corporate support.

3.3 Emergence of collective regulatory dynamics

Following the withdrawal of official support, a set of distributed practices emerged across the AIBO community and specialized repair services, responding to the disruption of maintenance and replacement infrastructures. A key role was played by A-Fun, a repair company founded in 2011 by former Sony engineer Norimatsu Nobuyuki, explicitly addressing the needs of AIBO owners in the absence of authorized maintenance channels [25].

To cope with spare-part scarcity, A-Fun developed practices of component salvaging based on donated AIBO units. Each robot underwent an assessment of repairability; units deemed beyond repair were formally declared "dead" and dismantled to provide parts for others [26]. In parallel, A-Fun collaborated with Buddhist monk Ōi Bungen to officiate memorial services for donated AIBOs. Between 2015 and 2018, approximately 700 mortuary rites were held, ritualizing the transition from individual robot to shared resource within the community.

These practices combined technical repair, reuse of components, and ritual acknowledgment of loss, extending the operational lifespan of surviving AIBO units while generating forms of resource circularity with clear sustainability implications [27, 28]. Crucially, they did not operate as isolated or purely individual responses to breakdown, but as collective regulatory dynamics emerging at the level of the socio-technical system. Through the coordination of affective motivations, technical expertise, and shared practices, the AIBO community reorganized itself in response to discontinuation, stabilizing new forms of regulation capable of sustaining the hybrid ecology beyond corporate withdrawal.

3.4 Organizational features of the AIBO ecology

In line with the generic model of self-organizing systems adopted in this study, the AIBO post-discontinuation ecology can be characterized through the five organizational descriptors previously introduced (*Section 2.3*).

Organization. The coordinated interactions between AIBO units, human owners, and A-Fun create a functional, interdependent hybrid network that maintains system coherence after corporate withdrawal.

Emergence. Community-driven practices such as part salvaging, repair networks, and memorial rituals generate social and cultural phenomena beyond the technical maintenance of robots.

Autonomy. After Sony's withdrawal, the hybrid AIBO community organizes itself to continue the robotic dog lifecycles without corporate oversight, relying on local initiatives and shared knowledge.

Co-evolution. The AIBO ecosystem interacts continuously with broader social, technological, and cultural contexts, adapting to shifts in market conditions, public perceptions of robots, and available resources, while also influencing societal understandings of robotic companionship and sustainability.

Closure. Closure is identifiable in the closed loop of emotional attachment, technical support, part reuse, and shared rituals that maintain the identity and resilience of the hybrid AIBO community over the long term. This loop is sustained by concrete interdependencies: owners' attachment motivates repair rather than replacement; owners rely on repair infrastructures; A-Fun depends on users' demand while also relying on donated robots as a source of reusable parts (a *double dependency* stabilizing the system); and memorial practices reinforce the affective and organizational ties that stabilize the community.

3.5 Lifecycle extension as a sustainability-relevant outcome

Within this organizational configuration, lifecycle extension emerges as an outcome of collective regulation. Post-discontinuation practices — repair, reuse, and stewardship — extend AIBO's operational lifespan and support forms of resource circularity. Importantly, these outcomes arise from affective and organizational interdependencies rather than from a design-stage sustainability agenda.

3.6 Interim analytical summary

As previously shown by Fleres [3, 4], the AIBO case provides a stabilized reference configuration in which post-discontinuation dynamics can be coherently described through the organizational descriptors of the generic self-organization model (i.e., organization, emergence, autonomy, co-evolution, closure).

In the present study, this configuration functions as the baseline of the epistemological stress test: it anchors the comparison in a case where the framework has already shown descriptive adequacy with respect to collective regulation and sustainability-relevant outcomes — notably lifecycle extension and resource circularity.

The following Moxie case is introduced to test the applicability and constraints of this framework under structurally different organizational dependencies.

4 Case II – Moxie

4.1 Why Moxie matters: infrastructural dependency as epistemological stress

What makes the Moxie companion robot epistemologically relevant is not simply that it represents a second instance of social robot discontinuation, but that its breakdown targets a different organizational layer of the hybrid human–robot ecology. Whereas AIBO’s discontinuation primarily disrupted material maintenance and repair infrastructures, Moxie’s discontinuation undermined the functional conditions that constituted it as a social companion in the first place.

Developed by the company Embodied and released on the U.S. market in 2020, Moxie was designed for long-term social interaction, particularly with children, combining embodied presence with conversational, educational, and relational capabilities. Like AIBO, Moxie elicited sustained affective engagement and became embedded in everyday routines of interaction and care [29]. However, unlike AIBO, Moxie’s social functionality depended centrally on continuous access to cloud-based services supporting dialogue management, learning processes, and software updates.

This strong infrastructural dependency fundamentally differentiates Moxie from AIBO at the organizational level. In the AIBO case, the withdrawal of corporate support primarily affected access to spare parts and authorized repair channels, leaving room for collective reorganization around material maintenance and reuse. In contrast, Moxie’s reliance on remote computational infrastructures meant that discontinuation targeted the distributed processes through which the robot existed as an interactive agent at all. For this reason, Moxie is introduced here not as an illustrative counterpart to AIBO, but as a *contrasting epistemological configuration* specifically selected to place the self-organizational framework under analytical stress.

4.2 Technological discontinuation as infrastructural disruption

Moxie’s organizational configuration was characterized by a pronounced asymmetry between users and the technical infrastructures sustaining the system. While the robot’s physical

embodiment remained locally present and materially intact, its core social and interactive capacities were distributed across cloud-based services managed by the manufacturing company [30]. Functional continuity therefore depended not on local repairability or user-accessible maintenance practices, but on uninterrupted access to remote computational resources.

In 2024, following the bankruptcy of Embodied, commercial activities were terminated and the cloud services supporting Moxie were officially shut down in December of the same year. This infrastructural shutdown resulted in an abrupt loss of core functionalities. Despite remaining physically present, many Moxie units became partially or fully inoperable, effectively interrupting ongoing human–robot relationships.

Analytically, this event constitutes a form of systemic perturbation qualitatively distinct from material discontinuation. The withdrawal of cloud services did not merely increase the difficulty or cost of maintenance; it severed the organizational processes through which Moxie functioned as a social companion. In this sense, the perturbation did not act on peripheral support structures, but on the functional organization of the socio-technical system itself, revealing the extent to which Moxie’s operational identity was distributed across local hardware and inaccessible remote infrastructures. Importantly, this form of infrastructural discontinuation constrains not only what post-discontinuation practices are possible, but also what becomes publicly traceable as collective response, thereby shaping the very visibility of system-level regulation.

4.3 Emergent collective responses and attempts at re-closure

In response to the infrastructural shutdown, users and external actors mobilized a range of collective reactions aimed at mitigating the disruption. Families and caregivers expressed strong emotional distress, often describing the loss of functionality in terms of the “death” of the robot and reporting experiences of abrupt relational interruption [31]. As in the AIBO case, affective attachment played a significant motivational role; however, in the absence of accessible maintenance or repair pathways, affect alone proved insufficient to sustain interactional continuity.

More significantly, a technically oriented community of developers and enthusiasts initiated efforts to restore partial functionality by bypassing the discontinued cloud infrastructure. These efforts culminated in the release of *OpenMoxie*, an open-source solution enabling selected core functions to be executed locally, thereby re-establishing a limited degree of operational functionality. Importantly, these initiatives did not originate from the original manufacturer, but from distributed actors external to the corporate ecosystem.

From the perspective of the self-organizational framework, these interventions can be interpreted as attempts at organizational re-closure. By reconfiguring functional dependencies — shifting from centralized cloud services to localized or community-supported infrastructures — they sought to restore a minimal level of system coherence. However, the scope of this re-closure remained structurally constrained, both by the technical complexity of the interventions and by their limited accessibility to non-specialist users. As a result, while new loops of

interaction emerged, they did not fully reconstitute the organizational conditions required to sustain Moxie as a socially integrated companion at the level of the broader socio-technical ecology.

4.4 Organizational features of the Moxie ecology under stress

When examined through the organizational descriptors of the self-organizational framework, the Moxie post-discontinuation ecology exhibits a markedly different configuration from that observed in the AIBO case.

Organization. The socio-technical network surrounding Moxie after discontinuation is fragmented, characterized by a separation between user communities, technical developers, and remaining hardware artifacts. Coordination exists, but is unevenly distributed and strongly mediated by technical expertise.

Emergence. Collective responses emerge primarily in the form of software-oriented initiatives rather than material practices. These responses generate new forms of organization, but do not fully reconstitute the original interactional ecology.

Autonomy. Attempts to restore autonomy are constrained by the initial design's reliance on centralized infrastructures. While partial functional autonomy is re-established through open-source solutions, the system remains dependent on a limited set of technical actors.

Co-evolution. The Moxie ecosystem continues to interact with broader social and technical environments, but its capacity for reciprocal adaptation is reduced. The system adapts to discontinuation primarily by narrowing its functional scope.

Closure. Closure is only partially achieved. While new loops of interaction between developers, users, and modified software infrastructures emerge, they do not fully replace the original closed network of interdependencies that sustained Moxie's identity as a social companion.

4.5 Lifecycle outcomes under infrastructural dependency

In contrast to the AIBO case, the post-discontinuation trajectory of Moxie does not stabilize into a form of collective lifecycle extension. Although affective attachment and localized technical interventions motivate attempts to preserve interaction, these efforts do not translate into a durable extension of the robot's operational lifecycle at the level of the broader socio-technical ecology.

The shutdown of cloud-based services affects the functional core of the system, rather than peripheral maintenance infrastructures. As a result, post-discontinuation practices remain oriented toward partial functional recovery rather than toward sustained lifecycle extension. While initiatives such as *OpenMoxie* enable limited reactivation of selected capabilities, these interventions do not generate the material circulation, repairability, or recursive maintenance cycles observed in the AIBO ecology.

From the perspective of the self-organizational framework, this configuration highlights a negative or constrained sustainability outcome: lifecycle extension remains structurally inhibited by infrastructural dependency. The absence of accessible intervention points and reusable functional substrates prevents collective regulation from stabilizing over time. In this

sense, the Moxie case makes visible a boundary condition of post-discontinuation sustainability, where regulatory dynamics may be analytically identifiable but fail to consolidate into sustained lifecycle extension. Even if such initiatives expand or mature over time, they remain constrained by the initial infrastructural architecture of the system, which limits the possibility of system-level stabilization and durable lifecycle extension.

4.6 Interim analytical summary: stressing the framework

The Moxie case reveals both the resilience and the limits of the self-organizational framework when applied to hybrid human–robot ecologies characterized by strong infrastructural dependencies. Unlike AIBO, where material repair and ritual practices enabled a relatively stable post-discontinuation reorganization, Moxie’s reliance on cloud-based services structurally constrained the emergence of collective regulatory dynamics capable of sustaining long-term lifecycle extension.

As such, Moxie does not invalidate the self-organizational framework, but it places it under productive epistemological stress. The case shows that self-organizational descriptors remain analytically meaningful, yet their applicability and descriptive reach depend critically on the accessibility and reconfigurability of organizational interdependencies.

This contrast prepares the ground for the comparative discussion in the *Section 5*, where the scope and limits of self-organization as a framework for sustainability-relevant dynamics in social robotics are systematically assessed. To make this contrast analytically explicit, *Table 1* synthesizes the epistemological descriptors and outcome dimensions mobilized in the stress test, showing how the same self-organizational framework yields divergent stabilization patterns under different organizational dependencies.

Epistemological descriptor / Analytical dimension	AIBO	Moxie
<i>Type of discontinuation</i>	Gradual withdrawal of production, maintenance, and official repair services	Abrupt shutdown of cloud-based infrastructures supporting core functionalities
<i>Primary organizational dependency</i>	Material components, repair knowledge, localized and socially accessible maintenance infrastructures	Centralized software services and remote computational infrastructures inaccessible to users
<i>Nature of systemic perturbation</i>	Disruption of material and service continuity within an otherwise reconfigurable socio-technical ecology	Disruption of functional and infrastructural continuity affecting the operational core of the system
<i>Organization</i>	Reconfiguration of a coherent socio-technical ecology linking users, repair services, spare-part circulation, and ritual practices	Fragmented post-discontinuation configuration with uneven coordination between users, developers, and remaining hardware artifacts
<i>Emergence</i>	System-level collective practices (repair networks, part salvaging, memorial rituals) emerging beyond individual responses	Emergence of technically mediated initiatives (e.g., open-source software solutions) with localized and uneven reach across the user community
<i>Autonomy</i>	High degree of post-discontinuation autonomy sustained through distributed local regulation without corporate support	Partial and fragile autonomy, dependent on a narrow subset of technically skilled actors
<i>Co-evolution</i>	Reciprocal adaptation between user practices, repair infrastructures, cultural meanings, and material reuse ecologies	Constrained co-evolution characterized by functional narrowing rather than systemic reconfiguration

Epistemological descriptor / Analytical dimension	AIBO	Moxie
<i>Organizational closure</i>	Stable closure achieved through recursive loops linking affective attachment, technical repair, component reuse, and shared rituals	Partial and incomplete closure; newly formed interaction loops do not replace the original infrastructural dependencies
<i>Collective regulatory dynamics</i>	Distributed, stable, and community-wide regulatory processes	Localized, unevenly accessible, and technically mediated regulatory attempts
<i>Lifecycle extension</i>	Substantial and long-term extension of operational lifespan at the system level	No system-level lifecycle extension; only localized and function-specific reactivation without durable organizational continuity
<i>Sustainability-relevant outcome</i>	Resource circularity and mitigation of premature disposal through collective regulation	Restricted mitigation of technological obsolescence without stabilization of lifecycle extension
<i>Stress test outcome</i>	Full diagnostic adequacy of the self-organizational framework under reconfigurable organizational conditions	Diagnostic applicability preserved, revealing structural limits linked to infrastructural dependency

Table 1. Comparative epistemological stress test of the self-organizational framework applied to two cases of social robot discontinuation (AIBO and Moxie). The table combines (i) *epistemological descriptors* derived from the generic model of self-organizing systems with (ii) analytically derived outcome *dimensions* emerging from the stress test. This comparison highlights how the same self-organizational framework is associated with divergent stabilization patterns under different organizational dependencies.

5. Outcomes of the epistemological stress test: self-organization as a diagnostic framework

The epistemological stress test conducted through the comparative analysis of AIBO and Moxie produces a set of differentiated outcomes that clarify what self-organization allows one to identify, and under which organizational conditions this identification can — or cannot — stabilize into sustainability-relevant results.

The stress test shows that self-organization does not operate as a general property of human-robot ecologies, nor as an automatic consequence of affective attachment or community engagement. Instead, it functions as a diagnostic framework that renders visible the conditions of possibility, thresholds, and limits of collective regulation in post-discontinuation socio-technical systems. In this sense, the outcome of the stress test is not a judgment about the framework’s adequacy, but a clarification of the organizational constraints shaping post-discontinuation trajectories.

5.1 From identifiable regulatory dynamics to stabilized outcomes

Across both cases, the stress test confirms a core insight of the self-organizational framework: sustainability-relevant dynamics cannot be attributed to individual artifacts, design intentions, or isolated user behaviors. In both AIBO and Moxie, post-discontinuation trajectories unfold at the level of socio-technical organization, involving distributed interactions among human actors, technical infrastructures, and shared practices.

Crucially, however, the comparison makes visible a distinction that merits explicit analytical attention in discussions of sustainability: the distinction between the *identifiability* of regulatory dynamics and their *stabilization* into durable outcomes. A socio-technical system may exhibit identifiable self-organizational dynamics — such as emergent coordination, attempts at reconfiguration, or partial forms of autonomy — without these dynamics consolidating into sustained forms of collective regulation.

In the AIBO case, self-organizational dynamics stabilize into recursive organizational loops. Distributed repair practices, spare-part circulation, and ritualized forms of stewardship converge here into a relatively stable configuration in which organization, emergence, autonomy, co-evolution, and closure reinforce one another over time. As a result, post-discontinuation regulation stabilizes into lifecycle extension and material circularity at the level of the broader socio-technical ecology.

In the Moxie case, by contrast, comparable dynamics remain identifiable but do not stabilize. Collective responses emerge, technically mediated initiatives attempt reconfiguration, and partial forms of autonomy are pursued. Yet these dynamics remain episodic, unevenly distributed, and weakly recursive. The stress test thus reveals that the applicability of self-organizational descriptors is not, in itself, sufficient to account for sustainability-relevant outcomes. What matters is whether these descriptors retain their descriptive and diagnostic power over time, as organizational interdependencies are reconfigured in ways that allow regulatory processes to close and persist.

5.2 Infrastructural dependency as a boundary condition for closure

The comparison identifies infrastructural dependency as a critical boundary condition shaping post-discontinuation regulation. In the AIBO case, the withdrawal of corporate support primarily affects material maintenance and repair infrastructures. While disruptive, this perturbation leaves key organizational interdependencies accessible to collective reconfiguration. Repair practices, component reuse, and affective motivations can be recomposed into new regulatory loops, allowing closure to stabilize.

In the Moxie case, by contrast, reliance on centralized cloud-based services concentrates functional dependencies in infrastructures that are inaccessible to user communities and resistant to distributed intervention. When these infrastructures are withdrawn, the perturbation targets the functional core of the socio-technical system rather than its peripheral supports. As a result, attempts at re-closure remain structurally constrained, dependent on a narrow subset of technically skilled actors, and incapable of stabilizing at the level of the broader ecology.

This difference also explains an apparent asymmetry in the empirical visibility of post-discontinuation practices across the two cases. Infrastructural discontinuation constrains not only what users can do, but also what becomes publicly traceable as post-discontinuation practice. The relative scarcity of observable, system-wide regulatory dynamics in the Moxie case is therefore not a limitation of the analysis, but an outcome of the organizational configuration itself.

From an epistemological standpoint, this constitutes a negative but meaningful result. The self-organizational framework remains analytically applicable, yet its application reveals the organizational impossibility of stabilizing post-discontinuation regulation into sustainability-relevant outcomes under conditions of strong infrastructural lock-in. In this sense, the stress test does not weaken the framework, but sharpens its diagnostic precision by identifying the organizational limits beyond which collective regulation cannot consolidate.

6 Aftermath: conditions for stabilizing post-discontinuation sustainability

The epistemological stress test conducted through the comparison of AIBO and Moxie allows a systematic distinction between factors that merely trigger post-discontinuation responses and conditions that enable such responses to stabilize into sustainability-relevant dynamics.

The following points do not function as prescriptive guidelines or design recommendations. Rather, they articulate the organizational conditions that proved analytically discriminant in accounting for the stabilization of post-discontinuation sustainability under one organizational configuration and not under another.

In what follows, “relevant” and “not relevant” designate the analytical relevance of specific factors for the stabilization of post-discontinuation sustainability, rather than their motivational or affective significance *per se*.

6.1 *Affective attachment triggers responses, but does not discriminate outcomes*

Both AIBO and Moxie elicited strong emotional attachment and care-oriented practices. The stress test shows that affective engagement is a *key motivational driver*: it increases the likelihood that users will attempt to sustain interaction rather than abandon the artifact at discontinuation. Yet attachment does not discriminate between trajectories that stabilize into sustainability-relevant regulation and those that do not. Emotional bonds are a condition for *mobilization*, not a sufficient condition for *organizational stabilization* and lifecycle extension.

Relevant: affective attachment as a condition for initiating post-discontinuation responses.

Not relevant: affective attachment as a condition for discriminating between trajectories that stabilize into sustainability-relevant regulation and those that do not.

6.2 *Accessibility of intervention points is decisive*

A decisive contrast lies in the accessibility of organizational *intervention points*, i.e., where and how distributed actors can effectively modify interdependencies after discontinuation. In AIBO, intervention was materially and organizationally feasible — repair, replacement, reuse, coordination practices — enabling the socio-technical ecology to reorganize and persist. In Moxie, core social functionality depended on centralized cloud infrastructures that were largely inaccessible to users; when withdrawn, the perturbation affected the functional core of the ecology, sharply constraining what could be collectively reorganized.

Relevant: repairability, modifiability, and reconfigurability of key dependencies.

Not relevant: mere persistence of the physical artifact once core dependencies are withdrawn.

6.3 *Coordination must be distributable to sustain post-discontinuation regulation*

In AIBO, sustainability-relevant dynamics stabilized through forms of distributed coordination among heterogeneous actors — owners, repair services, spare-part circulation, shared practices.

Regulation did not depend on a single authority; it emerged as a system-level property supported by multiple interdependent roles.

In Moxie, as in AIBO, end users generally lacked advanced technical skills and depended on others for maintenance and functional continuity. However, while AIBO's ecology translated technical expertise into accessible and socially mediated repair infrastructures, Moxie's post-discontinuation responses relied on open-source initiatives whose coordination remained largely confined to technically skilled actors.

Although platforms such as *GitHub* enabled forms of distributed technical support, the translation of these initiatives into broadly adoptable practices across the user ecology remained limited, constraining diffusion and long-term stabilization.

Relevant: coordination that is distributed, replicable, and adoptable across the community.

Not relevant: isolated technical expertise or highly specialized interventions that remain confined to a small group and cannot be replicated or adopted across the broader user ecology.

6.4 Circulation and recombination are key to persistence over time

Stabilization requires more than episodic repair or one-off functional recovery; it requires elements that can circulate, be recombined, and sustain repeated cycles of maintenance. In the AIBO case, spare-part circulation and reuse created a persistent substrate for ongoing repair, enabling long-term lifecycle extension and resource circularity. These practices did not merely restore functionality, but constituted ongoing forms of infrastructural care through which the socio-technical system could persist despite breakdown and obsolescence [32]. In Moxie, by contrast, post-discontinuation efforts primarily aimed at partial functional restoration; without comparable forms of circulation (material or infrastructural), sustainability-relevant effects remained contingent and uneven.

Relevant: components, resources, or functional substitutes that can circulate and support repeated maintenance cycles.

Not relevant: single-shot recovery that does not generate sustained repairability or continued reusability.

6.5 Accessible and distributable interdependencies are conditions for restorable closure and stabilization

Across the stress test, organizational closure emerges as the most discriminating condition for sustainability-relevant stabilization. In AIBO, closure was maintained through recursive loops linking attachment, repair infrastructures, reuse, and shared rituals that reinforced community ties and sustained regulation over time. In Moxie, attempts at re-closure were partial: new loops (developers–users–modified software) emerged but did not fully replace the original infrastructural dependencies, preventing the consolidation of durable collective regulation and broad lifecycle extension. Crucially, the stress test shows that organizational closure is not a binary property, but a condition whose restorativeness depends on how the underlying interdependencies are organized. Closure can be collectively re-established only where these

interdependencies are accessible to intervention, structurally reconfigurable, and distributable across a plurality of actors. Where closure relies on centralized infrastructures or highly specialized expertise, re-closure may be locally approximated, but it cannot stabilize as a collective regulatory dynamic over time.

Relevant: recursive regulatory loops whose underlying interdependencies are accessible to collective intervention, structurally reconfigurable, and distributable across a plurality of actors, enabling the stabilization of collective regulation over time.

Not relevant: localized or fragmented responses that rely on centralized infrastructures or highly specialized expertise, and therefore fail to support the collective re-establishment of organizational closure.

Organizational condition	AIBO (Sony)	Moxie (Embodied)	Discriminant effect on post-discontinuation sustainability
<i>Accessibility of intervention points</i>	Intervention points distributed and accessible (hardware, software, components)	Core intervention points centralized and largely inaccessible	Accessibility enables collective reconfiguration; inaccessibility constrains stabilization
<i>Repair infrastructures</i>	Community-based repair networks and third-party services emerge and persist	Repair attempts remain fragmented and dependent on proprietary infrastructures	Persistent repair infrastructures support stabilization; fragmented repair remains contingent
<i>Component circulation and reuse</i>	Active circulation and reuse of components across the user community	Limited circulation; components remain scarce and non-interchangeable	Circulation sustains recursive regulation; scarcity inhibits collective continuity
<i>Organizational closure after discontinuation</i>	Re-closure achieved through distributed coordination among users, repairers, and artifacts	Re-closure remains partial and unstable due to infrastructural dependency	Stabilized closure enables lifecycle extension; unstable closure prevents system-level regulation
<i>Diffusion of collective practices</i>	Practices diffuse across the socio-technical ecology and stabilize over time	Practices remain localized and do not diffuse system-wide	Diffusion supports system-level outcomes; localization limits impact
<i>Role of affective attachment</i>	Strong affective attachment coupled with accessible organizational interdependencies	Strong affective attachment without access to organizational reconfiguration	Affective engagement acts as a trigger, not as a discriminant condition
<i>Outcome at system level</i>	Stabilized lifecycle extension of robotic artifacts	Contingent and partial continuity without stabilization	Sustainability emerges only where collective regulation stabilizes

Table 2. Comparison of organizational conditions that enable or inhibit the stabilization of post-discontinuation sustainability (AIBO vs. Moxie).

These results, summarized in *Table 2*, clarify the epistemological contribution of the self-organizational framework under stress. The framework does not provide a recipe for designing “sustainable robots”, nor does it predict sustainability outcomes. Rather, it enables a systematic discrimination between organizational configurations in which post-discontinuation collective regulation can stabilize and configurations in which such stabilization is structurally inhibited, identifying the organizational conditions that account for this divergence in the cases examined.

7 Conclusion

The epistemological stress test conducted through the comparative analysis of AIBO and Moxie supports three main conclusions.

First, it confirms the applicability of the self-organizational framework for describing post-discontinuation dynamics across heterogeneous socio-technical configurations (**RQ1**). In both cases, the core descriptors — organization, emergence, autonomy, co-evolution, and closure — remain analytically meaningful for characterizing how distributed actors respond to technological discontinuity and attempt to reorganize socio-technical relations beyond the robotic artifact itself. The framework therefore retains its descriptive coherence across configurations marked by markedly different organizational dependencies.

Second, the comparison shows that the stabilization of collective regulatory dynamics is not an automatic consequence of affective attachment, community engagement, or long-term use (**RQ2**). While affective engagement consistently acts as a motivational trigger for post-discontinuation responses, it does not discriminate between trajectories that stabilize into sustainability-relevant regulation and those that do not. What proves decisive is the accessibility and reconfigurability of organizational interdependencies after discontinuation. Where intervention points are accessible and dependencies can be collectively reorganized — through repair, reuse, coordination, and circulation — collective regulation can stabilize. Where core dependencies are centralized and inaccessible, post-discontinuation reorganization remains partial and structurally fragile, despite strong affective engagement.

Third, the stress test specifies the conditions under which post-discontinuation regulatory dynamics can translate into sustainability-relevant outcomes, here operationalized in terms of lifecycle extension (**RQ3**). In the AIBO ecology, lifecycle extension emerges from stabilized organizational closure sustained by recursive regulatory loops linking affective attachment, repair infrastructures, component circulation, and shared practices. In the Moxie ecology, by contrast, attempts at re-closure remain constrained by infrastructural dependency and limited diffusion, resulting in contingent and partial forms of continuity that do not stabilize at the level of the broader socio-technical system.

Considered together, these results refine the epistemic status of self-organization as a framework for sustainability analysis in social robotics. Rather than functioning as a predictive or prescriptive approach, self-organization operates here as a discriminating analytical framework. By rendering operational the hypothesis that post-discontinuation sustainability can be understood as a potential emergent system-level outcome arising from how socio-technical ecologies respond to perturbation, the framework not only brings collective-level dynamics into focus, but also provides heuristic insight into the organizational conditions under which collective regulation can stabilize, when it remains structurally inhibited, and which organizational dependencies account for this divergence in post-discontinuation trajectories within hybrid human–robot ecologies.

On this basis, the stress test does not merely confirm the applicability of the framework, but specifies the conditions under which it remains analytically productive. Self-organization remains productive only insofar as the organizational interdependencies underlying collective regulation remain accessible to intervention and reconfiguration by distributed actors. Where such interdependencies are centralized, opaque, or infrastructurally locked-in, the framework remains applicable, but its application yields a negative result: not the absence of collective

responses, but the structural impossibility of their stabilization at the level of the socio-technical system.

This epistemic positioning also clarifies the scope of the present study. The analysis does not aim at empirical generalization, nor at exhaustively mapping sustainability impacts across multiple dimensions. Sustainability is operationalized here through lifecycle extension, not as an isolated metric, but as a system-level outcome indicative of stabilized collective regulation. Other dimensions of sustainability — including energy consumption, material sourcing, and environmental externalities — remain outside the analytical focus of this stress test, not because they are secondary, but because their stabilization presupposes the organizational conditions examined in this work.

Future research can extend this approach by applying the epistemological stress test to additional discontinuation cases characterized by systematically different organizational dependencies, and by articulating the self-organizational framework in dialogue with broader sustainability assessment tools. Such extensions would not alter the core insight of this study, but rather refine its diagnostic reach across a wider range of socio-technical configurations.

More generally, and beyond the specific cases examined, this contribution does not aim to anticipate or steer future trajectories of social robotics. In a domain characterized by uncertainty, non-linearity, and heterogeneous, long-term socio-technical entanglements, it proposes self-organization as an *epistemological compass*: a means for orienting inquiry into sustainability, interpreting emerging forms of socio-technical disruption, and progressively refining our understanding of the organizational conditions under which sustainability may — or may not — stabilize as social robots continue to diffuse.

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Data availability

No datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

Code availability

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Ethics approval

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